

A path towards a model? Political career paths of Polish presidents

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Abstract

Presidential elections in Poland are considered the most important election, next to parliamentary elections. This is because the President is elected by universal suffrage and has a strong popular mandate. It seems, therefore, that this office should be the culmination of a political career. The main objective of this paper is to define the place of the office of the President of the Republic of Poland on the model path of political careers of Polish politicians. In order to realize the main objective, two specific objectives have been identified: (1) to identify the model of the political career path of Polish presidents before taking office; (2) to identify the model of the political career path of Polish presidents after the presidency. A case study analysis of the political careers of successive presidents after 1989 was used in the analysis. Conclusions from the considerations indicate that while holding the office of the President of the Republic of Poland ends a political career, the only common feature of presidential candidates before winning the elections is their affiliation with one of the two largest political parties during the period of struggle for the presidency. In addition, the evolution over time shows that successive elections are won by candidates with less and less political experience so the election, although crucial, is basically another part of the party competition and a plebiscite between political groupings.

Keywords

Presidential election; political career paths; political career model; Republic of Poland

Introduction

Presidential elections fulfil diverse functions, which are often determined depending on the shape of the political system of a particular state (Blais, Massicotte and Dobrzynska, 1997; Hernandez-Huerta, 2017; Jones, 2001; Lewis-Beck and Rise, 1984; Mieczkowski, 2020). The political transformations made in Central and Eastern Europe in the late 1980s and early 1990s introduced interesting systemic solutions (Antoszewski, 2006; Antoszewski and Herbut, 1998). The emergence of the corrective presidency and thus the expansion of the competences of the head of state with the adoption of a parliamentary-cabinet system of government strengthened presidential offices (Baylis, 1996; Hlousek, 2013; Hofmann, 2002; Sedelius, 2006; Szymczak, 1994; Wojtasik, 2012). In addition, the adoption in many countries of universal suffrage as the method for electing the head of state, rather than parliamentary elections as a model for the chosen regime, has resulted in the president having the strongest popular mandate (Gebethner, 1998; Słomka, 2023).

Against this background, the case of Poland is particularly interesting, where not only do presidential elections seem to evolve towards a party plebiscite rather than a personal plebiscite (Jagielski, 2023; Peszyński, 2023), but very often this election, although crucial, becomes a proxy for the results of the next parliamentary election occurring after the presidential election (Pieniężny, 2025).

Additionally, an important feature of presidential elections in Poland is the potential for shaping the party system. Except for the largest parties/alliances, during the electoral campaign period the candidates of smaller parties/alliances seem to be fighting for the survival of their groupings and for a favorable result in the upcoming parliamentary elections, to which a good result in the presidential elections is supposed to contribute. It is also interesting to note the specific cases of candidates who, after obtaining a favorable result in the presidential elections, founded their political parties, which later found their way into parliament, such as Paweł Kukiz with his Kukiz'15 party in 2015, or even managed to enter the governing coalition, such as Szymon Hołownia and Poland 2050 as part of the Third Way in 2023 (Jagielski, 2024; Peszyński, 2023; Pieniężny, 2025; Wojnicki, 2024).

Pointing to these important features, which undoubtedly situate presidential elections in Poland alongside parliamentary elections as first-order elections (Reif and Schmitt, 1980; Reif, Schmitt and Norris, 1997; Hix and Marsh, 2011), it seems that the presidential office should represent the pinnacle of political career for politicians who hold this office. In view of this assumption, I set as the main objective of the present study the identification of the place of the office of the President of the Republic of Poland on the model path of political careers of Polish politicians. To realize this main objective, I have also indicated two specific objectives: (1) to identify the model of the political career path of Polish presidents before taking office; (2) to identify the model of the political career path of Polish presidents after the end of their presidency. The realization of these objectives made it possible to pinpoint the features and political functions common to the candidates who won the presidential election during their struggle for the presidency, as well as their political careers after the presidency.

To achieve the objectives set for this study, I also formulated research problems to be solved. The main research problem was as follows: What place in the model path of political careers of Polish politicians does the office of the President of the Republic of Poland occupy? I also proposed two specific questions: (1) Is there a model path of the political career of Polish presidents before taking office? (2) Is there a model political career path of Polish presidents after the presidency? Importantly, the time of the study covers the perspective of the Third Republic, i.e. the period since 1989. This is important because during the People's Republic of Poland the office of the President of the Republic

of Poland did not function, apart from the purely titular office of the President of the Republic of Poland in exile (Kozerska and Scheffler, 2017; Kozłowski, 2024), while the earlier history of the office, during the Second Republic, i.e. even before World War II, is too distant and the systemic conditions too different from those of the present (Dudek, 2021; Kowalski, 2008).

Data and methods

In view of the proposed research objectives and the research problems to be solved, I considered it best to conduct a case study of all the presidents of Poland after 1989 (Crasnow, 2022; Gerring, 2004; Lowi, 2013) and a subsequent comparative analysis of them (Mahoney and Rueschemeyer, 2003; Schneider and Wagemann, 2012). For this purpose, I used data provided by the State Electoral Commission. During my analysis, I also employed content analysis, in terms of information about the presidents' activities before and after they were in office, to determine model career paths.

Thus, the analysis presented in this study covered nine presidential elections and seven presidents (Aleksander Kwaśniewski and Andrzej Duda have both won the elections twice). The way the study was prepared and conducted is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The procedure of conducting the research.

Source: the author, based on Pieniężny, 2025.

The structure used in conducting the analyses allowed not only for the identification of common and differentiating features of the political careers of successive Polish presidents before and after the presidency, but also for the identification of the dependencies resulting from the evolution of the presidential election function in Poland (Pieniężny, 2025) and the manner of candidate selection (Hartliński, 2016; Kaczorowska, 2022).

Theoretical background

The issue I have taken up connects to an important extent with the area of research on political career paths. Research in this area has been conducted for many years in Western Europe (Borchert and Stolz, 2011; Canon, 1990; Stolz, 2003; 2011), and in recent decades also in Poland (Majcherkiewicz, 2017; Nyckowiak, 2013; Trzcńska & Witt, 2020). Determining the place of presidential elections on the model path of political careers in Poland requires the application of two fundamental theoretical concepts.

The first of these is the second-order elections theory (Reif and Schmitt, 1980; Reif, Schmitt and Norris, 1997; Hix and Marsh, 2011), which allows us to place the presidential election in Poland in the context of other elections, deriving the possible place of this election on the model path of political careers in Poland. The second approach, on the other hand, is precisely the theoretical indication of a model career path in Poland, in the context of setting the presidential election on it. Here, I draw on the results of my own long-term research on political career paths in Poland, conducted together with Arkadiusz Lewandowski (Lewandowski, 2020; Lewandowski and Pieniężny, 2024a; 2024b; 2024c; Pieniężny, 2025).

In view of this assumption, in the context under analysis I consider the distinction made in the second-order elections theory, which assumes a division of elections into category I elections, i.e. national elections: presidential and parliamentary elections, and category II elections, i.e. local elections: in Poland these will be local government elections and supranational elections, elections to the European Parliament, to be valid (Reif and Schmitt, 1980; Reif, Schmitt and Norris, 1997; Hix and Marsh, 2011).

Robert Wiszniowski (2008: 208-209) pointed to the lower mobilization of voters during these elections, but also to their plebiscitary nature, providing an opportunity to express dissatisfaction with those in power, as essential features of second-order elections. Reversing this assumption to the context of the presidential elections I am interested in, it should be pointed out that the features of this election, as a category I election, are: greater mobilization of voters, greater importance of strategic voting in relation to other, less significant elections, and abandoning (especially in the context of the crucial second round of the presidential election) natural preferences, often choosing the better of the candidates or voting negatively - against the other one (Pieniężny, 2025; Wiszniowski, 2008; Wojtasik, 2010; Wojtasik, 2012).

The division presented assumes a certain relationship between the different elections. First-order elections are in fact influenced by other elections that are also considered to be crucial, so that presidential elections are influenced by parliamentary elections and vice versa (Reif and Schmitt, 1980). What is important, however, is above all the point at which the different elections temporally situate themselves between each other (Wondreys, 2023). Very importantly in the context of this study, the elections immediately preceding the parliamentary election often take the form of a plebiscite in which voters express their support or disapproval for those in power or foreshadow the electoral outcome in the upcoming election (Wojtasik, 2010).

Such a situation occurred in Poland in 2015, when Andrzej Duda won the presidential election and Law and Justice (PiS) took over independent rule in the country for eight years. Although, of course, the reasons for the alternation of power are complex and cannot be attributed solely to success in the presidential elections, the victory of Andrzej Duda, who was condemned to defeat after announcing his candidacy, was like the wind in the sails of the Law and Justice party ahead of the 2015 parliamentary elections (Markowski, 2016; Pieniężny, 2025; Szczerbiak, 2017).

The second fundamental theoretical approach, as already mentioned, is the identification of a model path of political careers in Poland, together with the theoretical embedding of presidential elections on it. The indicated position was to be verified in the course of the analysis conducted in this text. In line with the long-term research conducted by me together with Arkadiusz Lewandowski, we adopted the model of the political career path in Poland, which is presented in Figure 2.

The model pathway thus prepared is intended to embed the subsequent elections in relation to their importance. Importantly, I do not assume that politicians will complete the indicated path in its entirety. After all, it is natural to start one's political career at different levels or to jump two or

three rungs at a time. However, since the presidential election has been positioned at the very top, and is therefore the most important election, it must be assumed that candidates who win this election will effectively run in elections at least at the parliamentary level.

Figure 2. Model of political career path in Poland.

Source: the author, based on: Lewandowski, 2020; Lewandowski and Pieniężny, 2024a; 2024b; 2024c; Pieniężny, 2025

To summarize the theoretical underpinnings of the considerations leading to the analyses, it should be pointed out: (1) that presidential elections are first-order elections so it seems natural that candidates should be politically experienced and recognizable in the electorate, but also (2) that presidential elections should be the pinnacle of a political career in Poland.

The specifics of presidential elections in the Polish political system

As already mentioned, the office of the President of the Republic of Poland functioned in the Second Polish Republic, specifically since 1921. Although during the communist rule an attempt was made to preserve the continuity of state power, this should be considered a traditional element (Dudek, 2021; Kozłowski, 2024). The office was formally reinstated in 1989, still under the Sejm of the People's Republic of Poland. During the first presidential election, which was held by the parliament, the communist leader Wojciech Jaruzelski was elected to the office (Pleskot, 2024; Tokarski, 2018; Trembicka, 2016).

However, after the political changes, it was decided to elect the head of state in direct elections. Wojciech Jaruzelski's presidency was very short-lived, as already in 1990 the first general presidential election was held, which was won by the leader of the anti-communist opposition, Lech Wałęsa (Glajcar, 2016; Materska-Sosnowska, 2015). Since then, presidential elections have been held regularly in Poland - every five years.

The significance and specifics of presidential elections in Poland have evolved over time. While at the beginning, in 1989 and 1990, and partly even in 1995, the elections were held in accordance with the assumptions of the systemic transformation and constituted a plebiscite between the communists and the democratic opposition (in 1995 the rivalry was still between the legendary head of the Solidarity movement, Lech Wałęsa and Aleksander Kwaśniewski, a politician with roots in the Polish United Workers' Party (PZPR)), since 2000, and especially since 2005, the elections have been a plebiscite between the representatives of the two largest parties - Civic Platform and Law and Justice.

Significantly, however, the leaders of these parties gradually gave up the fight for the presidency and since 2015, presidential elections have been a competition between the lesser-known candidates of both these parties, with the leaders of smaller parties. Thus, presidential elections in Poland are now a plebiscite of support for political parties, as the experience, position and political skills of the candidates are losing importance (Pieniężny, 2025).

Similarly, the functions of presidential elections in Poland have evolved over time. Today, however, the universal functions of presidential elections can be considered to be: (1) the creative function, i.e. the real election of the head of state, (2) the legitimizing function, i.e. the transfer of the mandate to exercise power, (3) the mobilizing function, in relation to the electorate and subsequent elections, (4) the function of selection of political elites, (5) the function of ensuring control of those in power, (6) the function of enforcing political accountability, (7) the limited function of creating political programs, (8) the function of expressing the will of the electorate, or (8) the function of selecting a stable governmental majority (Alberski, 2002; Wojtasik, 2012). In recent years, presidential elections have also had the function of creating change in the party system (Pieniężny, 2025) and of creating, rather than merely selecting, political elites, as has been the case since 2015 (Marcinkiewicz and Stegmaier, 2016; Rupnik, 2025).

This is despite the fact that these elections undoubtedly constitute first-order elections. From the point of view of the political system, the position of the President in Poland is not limited to representing the country externally. The specific nature of the office under analysis and its broad prerogatives have significant consequences for the entire political system. The very fact of the head of state's election by universal suffrage gives the President a social mandate equal to that of the Sejm and Senate but, by virtue of the number of votes won, greater than that of any politician, including the Prime Minister. Such a legitimizing equation may become a source of tension between the parliament and the president, even assuming that the constitution seeks to counteract it (Antoszewski, 1999; Wojtasik, 2012).

The analysis of the negative competences of the President of the Republic, the practice of the real use of which is extremely important in Poland (Wicherek, 2025), is particularly relevant here. The possibilities of vetoing laws, referring them to the Constitutional Tribunal, co-creating foreign policy together with the government, including the necessity to consent to the appointment of ambassadors, indicate that the role of the President in the Polish political system significantly increases during the period of cohabitation. This is when the person holding this office becomes the only real obstacle to the introduction of legal changes and the pursuit of day-to-day policy by the government and the parliamentary majority behind it. In a situation where the president, the government and the parliamentary majority all come from the same party or coalition, the role of the President of the Republic of Poland is almost exclusively limited to representative functions (Pieniężny, 2025).

The political careers paths of the presidents of Poland

I have analyzed the political paths of the presidents' careers in two ways. The first part of the analysis concerns the careers of presidents before they took office. The set of all functions held by successive presidents is presented in Table 1.

Analyzing each case presented in the table, it is important to point out the system specificity of successive elections, assuming that the later the election, the greater the chances for candidates to gain political experience. The specificity of the systemic change applies particularly to the first two presidents. While Wojciech Jaruzelski was a president with a great deal of political experience, he gained it during the People's Republic of Poland, when elections in Poland were not democratic

(Siedziako, 2016). His membership in the ruling Polish United Workers' Party gave him an advantage over other politicians (Żukowski, 2013). This is perfectly evident in the example of Lech Wałęsa. This is because he did not have any experience of holding public office, as this was impossible due to the opposition nature of the power-fighting Solidarity, with which he was politically associated (Mażewski, 2021). However, this does not mean that he did not have political experience. Throughout his trade union involvement, he very often met with important world politicians (Thorpe, 2020).

Table 1. Political career paths of presidents before becoming the President of the Republic of Poland.

President of the Republic of Poland	Presidency period	Political career before presidency
Wojciech Jaruzelski	1989-1990	1961-1989: Member of the Sejm of the People's Republic of Poland 1968-1983: Minister of Defense 1981-1985: Prime Minister 1985-1989: Chairman of the Council of State
Lech Wałęsa	1990-1995	No political experience 1980-1989: Leader of the Solidarity movement
Aleksander Kwaśniewski	1995-2005	1991-1995: Member of the Sejm of the Republic of Poland 1985-1989: Minister - Member of the Council of Ministers
Lech Kaczyński	2005-2010	1989-1991: Senator of the Republic of Poland 1991-1993, 2001-2002: Member of the Sejm of the Republic of Poland 1992-1995: President of the Supreme Audit Office 2000-2001: Minister of Justice 2002-2005: Mayor of the Capital City of Warsaw
Bronisław Komorowski	2010-2015	1991-2010: Member of the Sejm of the Republic of Poland 2005-2007: Deputy Speaker of the Polish Sejm 2007-2010: The Speaker of the Polish Sejm 1990-1991, 1992-1993: Deputy Minister of Defense 2000-2001: Minister of Defense
Andrzej Duda	2015-2025	2011-2014: Member of the Sejm of the Republic of Poland 2014-2015: Member of the European Parliament 2006-2007: Undersecretary of State at the Ministry of Justice 2008-2010: Undersecretary of State at the Chancellery of the President of the Republic of Poland 2007-2011: Member of the State Tribunal
Karol Nawrocki	2025- still	No political experience 2021-2025: President of the Institute of National Remembrance

Source: the author, based on the National Election Commission.

Aleksander Kwasniewski's political career before winning the office of President of the Republic of Poland deserves special attention. Coming from the Polish United Workers' Party, and later from the post-communist Social Democracy of the Republic of Poland and its successor, the Democratic Left Alliance (Woliński, 2002), he gained experience both in the executive power, being a member of the Council of Ministers still in the People's Republic of Poland, and in the legislative power, holding a mandate as a member of the Polish Sejm. He was thus elected president directly after holding the position of MP.

The next two presidencies also share a common feature - namely the extensive political experience of both Lech Kaczyński and Bronisław Komorowski. Both of them, although they were not

leaders of their political parties, played very significant roles in them (Pieniężny, 2025). Both also had experience of political activity in the executive, at government level, and in the legislature, at parliament level.

However, the last two presidents are an excellent confirmation of the assumption of the evolutionary nature of the office of the President of Poland. This is because the presidential elections are changing from a competition between the strongest figures on the Polish political scene, to a plebiscite of support for the two largest political parties - Law and Justice and Civic Platform/Civic Coalition, whose leaders do not decide to run in the elections, fielding less well-known candidates (Pieniężny, 2025). This was the case with Andrzej Duda, who, although he has experience in public office in both the legislative and executive branches of government, was not a nationally recognizable politician before winning the presidential elections (Kołodziej, 2017). The situation is even more interesting in the case of Karol Nawrocki, who has never held office in the legislature or the executive, but was only the president of the Institute of National Remembrance, which is not a political entity (Reczek, 2015).

The entire analysis of the political careers of the Presidents of the Republic of Poland, prior to their assumption of office, does not allow for the identification of a single model career path for all those holding the office since 1989. Significantly, however, apart from the specificity of the transitional elections of 1989 and 1990, each successive president, until Karol Nawrocki in 2025, held a parliamentary seat during his career and, in the case of Andrzej Duda, also a parliamentary seat. Aleksander Kwaśniewski and Bronisław Komorowski resigned their Sejm mandates to take up the office of the President of the Republic of Poland, and Andrzej Duda resigned his seat in the European Parliament, confirming that the office of the President of the Republic of Poland is higher in the hierarchy according to politicians' evaluations. However, the attempt to indicate the model of the path of the political careers of the Presidents of the Republic of Poland is an evolutionary issue. The shape of this evolution is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Evolution of the political importance of presidents before taking office.

Source: the author.

When analyzing the paths of the political careers of the Presidents of the Republic of Poland after leaving office, I decided to present this phenomenon in the same way as in the earlier analysis. The paths of the presidents' political careers after their termination of office are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Political career paths of presidents after leaving office as the President of the Republic of Poland.

President of the Republic of Poland	Presidency period	Political career after presidency
Wojciech Jaruzelski	1989-1990	He has not stood for election in any election. He has not held any public office.
Lech Wałęsa	1990-1995	He lost the 1995 and 2000 presidential elections, after which he did not stand for election. He has not held any public office.
Aleksander Kwaśniewski	1995-2005	He has not stood for election in any election. He has not held any public office.
Lech Kaczyński	2005-2010	He died in a plane crash near Smolensk (Russia) while serving as the President of the Republic of Poland.
Bronisław Komorowski	2010-2015	He lost the 2015 presidential elections. He has not stood for election since then. He has not held any public office.
Andrzej Duda	2015-2025	He has not stood for election in any election. He has not held any public office.
Karol Nawrocki	2025- still	-----

Source: the author, based on the National Electoral Commission.

While in the case of the pre-presidential career paths of the presidents it was not possible to identify similarities concerning all the candidates, in the issue under analysis the similarities are obvious. None of the presidents, after completing two terms of their administrations or in the event of political defeat after their first term, chose to run for any other type of election or held any public office. The indicated phenomenon directly confirms that the presidency is therefore the pinnacle of political career in Poland, and past experience shows that, unlike in other types of elected functions, there is no phenomenon of vertical transition of specific candidates to a lower level, to a lower level election, and thus the election does not go beyond the paradigm of a one-way political career path (Borchert and Stolz, 2011; Stolz, 2003). In all cases analyzed, the function of President of the Republic was simultaneously the end of a political career.

Conclusions

Presidential elections in Poland undoubtedly meet the criteria for being recognized as first-order elections (Reif and Schmitt, 1980; Reif, Schmitt and Norris, 1997; Hix and Marsh, 2011). The very fact of electing the President in a direct election gives the person holding this office a very strong legitimacy and social mandate, which, combined with the broad prerogatives and especially their practical use by successive Presidents, makes the position of the President of the Republic of Poland very strong by the standards of the parliamentary-cabinet system operating in other countries of the world (Alberski, 2002; Antoszewski, 1999; Wicherek, 2025; Wojtasik, 2012). Having the office of the President of the Republic of Poland is very important for political parties from the point of view of the effectiveness of the exercise of power and the speed of the introduction of the assumed legal solutions. This is because without the consent of the President, the actual exercise of power is very difficult, and on many issues

even impossible. This is most evident when cohabitation occurs. Due to the indicated fact that having the president on one's side of a political dispute gives an advantage in the political system, parties field strong candidates, fighting hard for victory (Pięniężny, 2025).

Summing up, it should be pointed out that while there is a path for the political career of the presidents of the Republic of Poland after leaving office - the office ends the political career in all the cases of the presidents of the Republic of Poland, the only common feature of the political careers of the presidential candidates before winning the elections is their affiliation to one of the two largest political parties during the period of competing for the presidency (Pięniężny, 2025). Apart from the peculiarities of the 1989 and 1990 transitional elections and the more recent case of Karol Nawrocki in 2025, each of the presidents also held a seat in the Polish Sejm. Lech Kaczyński also held a Senator's mandate, while Andrzej Duda was also a Member of the European Parliament.

The evolution over time of the function and role of presidential elections in Poland makes it possible to distinguish three fundamental periods. During the reigns of the first three presidents, until 2005, the office was held by party leaders characterized by extensive (for the systemic conditions) political experience. The next two presidents, 2005 to 2015, were not leaders of their political parties, but their position was very strong and they were characterized by a very high level of political experience, both in the legislature and the executive. The perspective since 2015 (and possibly beyond) indicates that during this period, candidates with less and less political experience win elections.

With the high social polarization evident in Poland (Tworzecki, 2019), presidential elections are no longer becoming a competition between experienced, distinguished and recognizable politicians, but a party plebiscite in which the candidate is not the most important. Especially in the second round of elections, a mechanism of negative voting (for the lesser evil) has developed (Miedzińska, 2015).

However, what is very important, the whole of the conducted analysis allowed to fulfil the main objective of the research, which was to determine the place of the office of the President of the Republic of Poland on the model path of political careers of Polish politicians. Answering the main research problem (What place in the model path of political careers of Polish politicians does the office of the President of the Republic of Poland occupy?), it should be indicated that holding the office of the President of the Republic of Poland is the peak of the political career of Polish politicians. Giving such an answer was made possible by the specific objectives: (1) to identify a model of the political career path of Polish presidents before taking office; (2) to identify a model of the political career path of Polish presidents after the presidency and to answer the specific research problems: (1) Is there a model path of the political career of the presidents of Poland before taking office? (2) Is there a model political career path of the presidents of the Republic of Poland after the presidency? For while it is not possible to identify a single model of the political career path of the presidents of the Republic of Poland before taking office, due to the lack of common points for all cases, the termination of the office of the President of the Republic of Poland is tantamount to the termination of public office and candidacy in any type of election.

This does not mean that former presidents do not remain active, finding themselves in the orbit of the political sphere. They often take part in political events or comment on current disputes in the media. After Andrzej Duda left the presidency at the age of only 53, questions about the possibility of former presidents continuing to be politically active became more frequent in the public space. Perhaps, following the example of many European countries, Poland should provide former presidents with a seat in the Senate (Morel, 2020; Pasquino, 2002). However, this issue requires further analysis.

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